

Extremization of Entropy, Central Limit Theorem and Classical Statistical and Quantum Mechanics

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Extremization of entropy, usually subject to an average energy constraint, (Maxwell-Boltzmann gas) is often associated with maximization of the number of microstates N gas particles may represent. The math procedure of extremization (variational calculus) is then associated with the \ln of a factorial expression which reduces to $n(ei)\ln(n(ei))$ using Stirling's approximation.

The central limit theorem, on the other hand, states that the distribution of sample means of a random variable approaches a Gaussian, i.e. $\exp(-pp/(2\text{sig sig}))$. Here sig sig is the standard deviation. For a random variable, the important or characteristic information is the standard deviation associated with the average of the square pp . We suggest here that an alternative way of looking at maximization of entropy (which is a stability statement we argue) other than \ln of permutations is to consider the stability of the variation of the variance of pp subject to a change in the probability, with pp written in terms of $P(p)$. Average kinetic energy in a statistical problem represents such a variance and should be invariant under changes of the probability subject to an average kinetic energy constraint, we suggest.

How does this idea apply to quantum mechanics? In quantum mechanics, one has a statistical function $\exp(ipx)$ and for bound states creates $W(x)=\text{wavefunction} = \text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx)$. $a(p)a(p)$ is formally the probability for p , but this does not mean that $a(p)a(p)$ is a random variable because one has the constraint: $\text{Sum over } p \ a(p)a(p) \ pp^2/m + \text{Integral } dx \ V(x) \ W(x)W(x) = E_n$. In the case of a harmonic oscillator, however, one knows a priori that the two summands are each equal to $E_n/2$. Furthermore there are a set of E_n values, starting at a ground state and increasing. All E_n values, except the ground state, are metastable. Thus the ground state is a special state. Given that $\text{Sum over } p \ a(p)a(p)pp^2/m = E_0/2$, a priori, one may consider that all of the information of $a(p)a(p)$ is associated with E_0 . This is exactly the case for a Gaussian from the central limit theorem. Alternatively, from information theory, information = $\ln(\text{probability})$ which yields the same result. If this is the case, then $pp/2m \ a(p)a(p)$ written strictly in terms of $P(p)=a(p)a(p)$ should be stationary upon changing $P(p)$ subject to the $E/2$ constraint. This special situation, however, only holds for the ground state oscillator.

What about average potential energy for the ground state oscillator? If the probability for p (momentum) is a Gaussian due to the Central Limit theorem, this means that the standard deviation is the information (and is linked with randomness). Taking a Fourier transform of $a(p)$ cannot add more information to the picture, we argue. $W(x)W(x)$ should also be a Gaussian, as it is. As a result, $xxW(x)W(x)$, written in terms of $P(x)=W(x)W(x)$ subject to the same $E_0/2$ constraint should represent a maximization or stationary situation, we argue.

Extremization of Entropy and Maximum Number of States

It seems that there is a tradition of associating maximization of entropy with the maximization of the number of possible microstates N gas particles may take, subject to an average energy

constraint which approximates a total energy constraint (i.e. the microcanonical condition). This follows for the observation that:

$$\text{Entropy} = \ln \left\{ \frac{N!}{\prod_i n_i!} \right\} \text{ subject to } \sum_i e_i n_i = E_{\text{ave}} \quad ((1))$$

Using Stirling's approximation, $\ln(n!) \approx n \ln(n)$, ((1)) when maximized yields the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution $P(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$. This distribution, however, is equivalent to arguing that information $\ln(P)$, from information theory equals e_i/T where T is a parameter which makes e_i/T dimensionless and fixes average energy.

We suggest that there might be another way of interpreting maximization of entropy or the stationary situation of the equilibrium state. Physically, the maximization of states subject to an average energy constraint seems to imply that perturbing a gas by removing some possible microstates and then removing the restriction means that collisions will restore these microstates. In other words, fluctuations in the system should not break down the equilibrium, suggesting that it is a stable state. In math terms, this seems to be associated with an extremization or stationary state.

Central Limit Theorem

The Central Limit Theorem (1) states that sample average of a random variables approach a Gaussian probability distribution:

$$\exp(-p^2 / (2 \sigma^2)) \text{ where } \sigma \text{ is the standard deviation } ((2))$$

We interpret this as indicating that for a random variable, the information is represented by the standard deviation which is associated with the average:

$$\int p \exp(-p^2 / (2 \sigma^2)) dp \quad \text{if } \int p \exp(-p^2 / (2 \sigma^2)) dp = 0 \quad ((3))$$

In other words, the standard deviation is a way of characterizing the random variable p . This average ((3)), however, is equivalent to average kinetic energy for a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas. This seems to imply:

((A)) The condition for stability of a random variable is the stationary situation of its average kinetic energy subject to a change in probability.

In other words, ((3)) may be rewritten as: $\ln(P(p))$ constant $P(p)$ which may be varied subject to a constraint on average energy $\sum_p p^2 / (2m) P(p)$. This leads to the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution. Another way to state this is that average information is stationary subject to an average energy constraint, with the information being:

$$p^2 / m \quad ((4))$$

We ask whether this idea may be applied to quantum mechanics.

Central Limit Theorem and Quantum Mechanics

We have argued above that the Central Limit Theorem suggests that instead of extremizing the \ln of the number of states, one may extremize the average information pp which characterizes the distribution $\exp(-pp/(2\sigma^2))$. In other words, one extremizes:

$P(p) \ln(P)$ subject to an energy constraint.

In quantum mechanics, one has a statistical probability $\exp(ipx)$ and for bound states, creates:

wavefunction = $\sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$. ((5))

Then: $\{\sum_p a(p) pp/2m \exp(ipx)\} / W(x) + V(x) = E_n$ ((6))

From this: $\{\sum_p pp/2m a(p)a(p)\} + \int dx V(x)W(x)W(x) = E_n$ ((7))

The E_n 's represent a discrete set of energy values.

In other words, one does not see a $P(p)\ln(P)$ subject to an energy constraint form.

There is a special case, however, where one knows a priori the values of the two terms on the LHS side of ((7)). This case is the quantum harmonic oscillator. In such a case:

$\{\sum_p pp/2m a(p)a(p)\} = E_n/2$ and $\int dx V(x)W(x)W(x) = E_n/2$ ((8))

((8)) suggests that $a(p)a(p)$ and $W(x)W(x)$ have the same mathematical form, which they do, namely $W(x) = \exp(-.5 \sqrt{km} xx)$ and $a(p) = \exp(-.5 pp/\sqrt{km})$.

One may note that ((8)) holds for all E_n , but only E_0 , the ground state, is stable. The others are metastable. It seems there must be a special property associated with the ground state. If one considers:

$\{\sum_p pp/2m a(p)a(p)\} = E_0/2$ ((9)) (ground state is stable)

for the oscillator, it seems $a(p)a(p)$ may only be associated with the information $E_0/2$. From the Central Limit theorem one might expect $a(p)a(p) = \exp(-bpp)$. This is equivalent to a stationary variance. In other words:

Extremize $P(p)\ln(P(p))$ subject to $C pp^2/m P(p)$, where C is a Lagrange multiplier.

If one uses the Central Limit theorem to associate $a(p)a(p)$ with the random distribution $\exp(-b p p)$, then $a(p)$ is also associated with a Gaussian, i.e. carries the same kind of information. Taking an inverse Fourier transform to obtain $W(x)$ does not add information, so one expects the same randomness, i.e. a Gaussian again. (Actually taking the Fourier transform confirms this.) In other words, $W(x)W(x)$ should be associated with $\exp(-d x x)$ where d is a constant.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that maximization of entropy subject to an average energy constraint, often uses $\ln\{N! / \text{Product } n(e_i)!\}$ as entropy suggesting that the number of microstates is maximized. A stationary situation exists because if a fluctuation restricts some microstates, collisions restore them as there is no permanent constraint preventing them.

We ask: Is there another way to view such a stationary solution? We argue that the Gaussian form $\exp(-p p / (2 \text{sig sig}))$ from the Central Limit Theorem for a random variable suggests that the variance = sig sig characterizes a random distribution. In other words, the variance or $\int p p \exp(-p p / (2 \text{sig sig}))$ should be stationary to changes in $P(p)$ with $p p$ being written in terms of $P(p)$. We suggest that this is an alternative way in which to view the stationary behaviour of randomness i.e. equilibrium (subject to an average energy constraint). This may be applied to the kinetic energy of a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas.

We ask whether it may also be applied to a quantum bound state? In general, one does not have $\sum \text{over } p a(p)a(p) p p / 2m$ equal an known a priori value. In other words, $a(p)a(p)$ carries more information than simply information about E_n . In the harmonic oscillator case, however, $\sum \text{over } p a(p)a(p) p p / 2m = E_n / 2$. All states but the ground state are metastable, so we consider $E_0 / 2$. In such a case, the only information associated with $P(p)$ may be E_0 . For this solution to be stationary, one would suggest that $P(p) \ln(P)$ is stationary subject to a $p p / 2m P(p)$ constraint. This leads to a Gaussian for $a(p)$. $W(x)$ is the inverse Fourier transform of $W(x)$. It should not carry different information and so should also be a Gaussian, as may be formally shown.

Thus we suggest that maximization of entropy may be associated with the term $P(p) \ln(P(p))$ from considerations of the Gaussian of the central limit theorem instead of thinking in terms of maximization of the \ln of microstates.

References

- (1) https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Central_limit_theorem